

LESLLA Symposium Proceedings

Recommended citation of this article

Cole, S. M., & Ellson, A. B. (2015). Implementing the Mutually Adaptive Learning Paradigm in the LESLLA Classroom. *LESLLA Symposium Proceedings*, 10(1), 199–216.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8024423>

Citation for LESLLA Symposium Proceedings

This article is part of a collection of articles based on presentations from the 2014 Symposium held at Radboud University, Nijmegen, The Netherlands. Please note that the year of publication is often different than the year the symposium was held. We recommend the following citation when referencing the edited collection.

Van de Craats, I., Kurvers, J., & van Hout, R. (Eds.) (2015). *Adult literacy, second language and cognition*. Centre for Language Studies. Centre for Language Studies.

<https://lesllasp.journals.publicknowledgeproject.org/index.php/lesllasp/issue/view/474>

About the Organization

LESLLA aims to support adults who are learning to read and write for the first time in their lives in a new language. We promote, on a worldwide, multidisciplinary basis, the sharing of research findings, effective pedagogical practices, and information on policy.

LESLLA Symposium Proceedings

<https://lesllasp.journals.publicknowledgeproject.org>

Website

<https://www.leslla.org/>

IMPLEMENTING THE MUTUALLY ADAPTIVE LEARNING PARADIGM IN THE LESLLA CLASSROOM

Sara M. Cole and Allegra B. Elson, Greater Pittsburgh Literacy Council

Abstract

This paper describes a LESLLA researcher-practitioner partnership and traces the successes and challenges of practitioners implementing the Mutually Adaptive Learning Paradigm® (MALP®) instructional model at the Greater Pittsburgh Literacy Council, a community-based adult literacy program in Pittsburgh, PA, USA. Implementation was introduced in four classes: Bridge Literacy, Foundations, and two Family Literacy classes. Our initial findings suggest that use of MALP encouraged active participation, further developed a sense of community, reduced cultural dissonance, and encouraged greater LESLLA learner responsibility helping to enhance an already learner-centered curriculum.

Keywords: refugee, low-literate, adult education, classroom practices

1. Introduction

As more and more LESLLA students enter educational and training programs, there is a greater need to expand and enhance how practitioners work with these struggling learners. They are most likely to struggle because they find themselves confounded by the ways in which the language and content are presented, practiced, and assessed (DeCapua & Marshall 2011: ix). Researchers, too, continue to develop frameworks for best practices to help LESLLA learners succeed inside and outside the classroom while at the same time trying to connect with and support practitioners working with such students. How can these practitioners and researchers come together in a meaningful way to support each other's work? What is the best way for researchers and practitioners to work together in ways that benefit LESLLA students? This paper describes a LESLLA researcher-practitioner partnership and traces the successes and challenges of the practitioners implementing the Mutually Adaptive Learning Paradigm® (MALP®)¹ instructional model at a community-

Ineke van de Craats, Jeanne Kurvers and Roeland van Hout (eds.)

Adult literacy, second language and cognition

Nijmegen: CLS, 2015, pp. 199-216

based adult literacy program in Pittsburgh, PA, USA. After describing the program and its students, we'll examine and explain the MALP model, detailing implementation and assessing implications for further use.

2. Implementation site

The site of our implementation of the MALP instructional model is Greater Pittsburgh Literacy Council (GPLC), a community-based organization in Pittsburgh, PA, USA. GPLC provides instructional programs in ESL (English as a Second Language), GED (General Education Development) Preparation, workplace skills development, basic skills (reading, writing, math), and family literacy. All services provided to students are free. While GPLC has volunteer tutors providing one-to-one and small group instruction throughout the city, MALP implementation was realized at its Downtown Center location with full-time instructional staff experienced in working with LESLLA students. These instructors are responsible for classroom instruction of 10-20 students per class along with creating curriculum, lesson planning and materials development.

2.1. Placement procedures

Incoming ESOL students at GPLC are assessed with the *BEST Plus* (*Basic English Skills Test*²). *BEST Plus* is an individually administered, face-to-face oral interview designed to assess the English language proficiency of adult English language learners in the United States. *BEST Plus* is a combined test of listening and speaking skills. As an oral assessment, *BEST Plus* provides a short, practical test that meets the accountability needs of publically funded programs that report to the National Reporting System (NRS) (Elson & Krygowski 2012: 184).

In addition to the *BEST Plus*, GPLC also uses a writing sample to assess students. Students' writing abilities range from being able to write a few letters of the Roman alphabet to their full names and addresses. Some are able to write short sentences such as, *My name is* or *I am from*, some may be able to write a few words in their native language. Based on writing samples from students in classes that participated in the MALP implementation, they ranged from being nonliterate (learners who have had no access to literacy), semiliterate (learners who have had limited access to literacy instruction) or emergent readers (Elson & Krygowski 2012: 185).

2.2. Classes and students

The ESL classes offered to students range from Foundations to Advanced level. Most classes have around 10-15 students. During particularly busy times of the year, class size can grow to 20 students, but this is usually an anomaly. Classes are open-enrollment, open-entry and open-exit; new students can join the class at any time (and most refugees join soon after arriving in Pittsburgh), and students leave a class when test scores and informal assessments show they can advance or when they begin jobs (Elson & Krygowski 2012: 186). For the purpose of the MALP implementation, three classes were chosen, Foundations with students scoring at a 0-1 SPL (student performance level) / Beginning ESOL literacy level to Bridge Literacy with students scoring 2-3 SPL level / Low Beginning to High Beginning ESOL level to Family Literacy which has large ranges of students from Beginning to High Intermediate ESOL.

The students in the Downtown Center classes tend to be newly arrived Bhutanese refugees, along with Burmese and Iraqi refugees. There is now an influx of students from Central Africa (Rwanda, Congo, Burundi, Tanzania) in our classes as well. The students range in age from 25-70 years old, and the majority of them spent nearly 20 years in refugee camps.

3. Partnership

At the 2013 LESLLA Symposium, held in San Francisco, CA, USA, there was a call for researchers and practitioners to come together to share expertise. "The 'Partnerships in LESLLA' program aimed to stimulate a new culture of cooperation and collaboration in the LESLLA community" (2013 LESLLA Symposium program, p. 20). Allegra Elson, a GPLC instructor, attended the symposium and met researchers Andrea DeCapua and Helaine Marshall at their session: *Transitioning to Schooling: Reducing Cultural Dissonance in a Community-Based Literacy Program*. After some discussions at the symposium, Dr. Marshall visited GPLC where she presented the MALP instructional model to instructors and administrators. After follow-up meetings via Google Hangout, a partnership was formed that included three instructors from GPLC, Drs. DeCapua and Marshall, along with approval from GPLC's Associate Director. The partnership agreement was settled in the fall of 2013. The goals of this collaboration were to create an on-going partnership between the researchers and practitioners in order to evaluate the model and provide data for the researchers, improve methods for structuring and evaluating instruction for

practitioners and to help LESLLA students become more successful in our classrooms by reducing cultural dissonance (Ibarra 2001).

3.1. Mutually Adaptive Learning Paradigm

The MALP model and the philosophy that underpins it has been described extensively in other sources, therefore we will only treat it briefly in this article. Those who are interested in further information on the creation of the model and the research that informs it should refer to works by Dr. Andrea DeCapua and Dr. Helaine W. Marshall, the researchers who developed the model (Marshall & DeCapua 2011, 2013). Our focus here is instead upon what the implementation of this model looks like in our particular classrooms at GPLC. Some background and explanation, however, is, required to make sense of our implementation.

The Mutually Adaptive Learning Paradigm, or MALP, is an instructional model developed to help reduce cultural dissonance in students with limited or interrupted education. The model seeks to reduce cultural dissonance by combining the informal methods and conditions for learning that LESLLA, or SLIFE (students with limited or interrupted formal education, a term that MALP researchers use interchangeably with LESLLA) students bring to the table with the sort of activities and tasks needed to participate in a Western-style classroom (see Figure 1).

Two Different Learning Paradigms		
Aspects of Learning	SLIFE	U.S. Classrooms
CONDITIONS	Immediate Relevance	Future Relevance
	Interconnectedness	Independence
PROCESSES	Shared Responsibility	Individual Accountability
	Oral Transmission	Written Word
ACTIVITIES	Pragmatic Tasks	Academic Tasks

(Adapted from DeCapua & Marshall, 2009, 2011; Marshall, 1994, 1998)

Figure 1: *Two different learning paradigms. Adapted from DeCapua & Marshall 2009, 2011. Marshall 1994, 1998.*

MALP aims at reducing cultural dissonance in LESLLA students while at the same time helping them successfully transition to working within a Western-style classroom. Cultural dissonance here refers to “a sense of confusion and dislocation that students coming from different cultural backgrounds and ways on learning experience when confronted with the expectations and demands of Western-style formal education” (Ibarra 2001; Nieto 2010: 9, as cited in Marshall & DeCapua 2013). That is, LESLLA learners must not only learn a new language and, often times, new content material, but they must do so in ways that are largely unfamiliar as well, producing a sense of things being “off” and making learning less accessible to them in this environment (Marshall & DeCapua 2015). The model addresses the sense of dislocation that LESLLA students may face by adopting a blend of LESLLA student expectations for learning with the typical expectations of a Western classroom. The model accepts LESLLA learners’ conditions for learning (materials and subject matter immediately relevant to their lives, a feeling of interconnectedness with fellow classmates and the teacher). The model also combines both LESLLA and Western-style processes, or means through which students approach new material, by using the written word (Western-style) alongside oral transmission (LESLLA) and including opportunities for both shared responsibility (LESLLA) and individual accountability (Western-style) in the classroom. By providing conditions and processes that are familiar and comfortable for LESLLA students, students are then less likely to feel overwhelmed when they are asked to perform decontextualized tasks, the type of learning tasks expected in a Western classroom. In short, the model seeks to meet LESLLA students where they are when they arrive in Western classrooms while at the same time gradually introducing them to and preparing them to successfully participate in the learning culture of their new country (Marshall & DeCapua 2013).

During our initial meetings, we evaluated the model and saw that some of our classroom practices already fit the model while others did not. One of the ways that our classroom practices aligned with the model was our focus on immediately relevant content from our students’ lives. Given our student population and the urgency with which some needed to learn English, we were (and continue to be) constantly focusing on such material. We concentrate strongly on instruction and curriculum that take into account the life experiences, goals, family and workplace needs of our students, what Condelli and Wrigley (2006) call “bringing in the outside” (p. 127). Classroom practices that did not fit the model were a tendency to have Foundations level classes more teacher-centered with the teacher choosing all the topics, not creating enough opportunities for independent work, and not enough connections between oral and written tasks. As implementation began, our goal was to align

our teaching with the model, initially relying heavily on using the MALP checklist, a rubric of sorts, to plan lessons and develop materials (see Appendix).

Figure 2: *How the Mutually Adaptive Learning Paradigm blends LESLLA (SLIFE) learner expectations and western (U.S.) classroom learner expectations. Adapted from DeCapua & Marshall (2013: 32).*

3. Implementation

3.1. Sara's Bridge Literacy class

In Sara's afternoon Bridge Literacy class, the model was implemented with refugee students from Bhutan, Iraq, Somalia, Burundi, and Uzbekistan who scored 2 or 3 SPL levels on the Best Plus test. The class size ranges from 10-20 students at any given time. The model was used to create a Neighborhood unit, culminating in a student-developed Neighborhoods booklet. The core of the unit was an LEA (Language Experience Approach) based on the neighborhoods in which the students live. The Language Experience Approach, originally developed for teaching reading to native speakers of English (Van Allen & Allen 1967), is an instructional approach that has been adapted for use with ELLs. It uses a shared experience (a class trip, going to the doctor) as a prompt for speaking and writing. The instructor asks the students to recount the experience,

records the students' responses and uses them as a reading text for the class. LEA is a way to create learner-generated texts and is an efficient technique in working with emergent readers as it connects what they are able to communicate orally to what they are learning to do in print (Crandall & Peyton 1993 as cited in Vinogradov 2010). The aforementioned MALP checklist (DeCapua & Marshall 2011; see Appendix A) played a major role in lesson planning, creating a framework for the activities that culminated in the students creating their own booklet. The checklist was used to plan and ensure LESLLA learner expectations were accommodated while simultaneously beginning to introduce the students to decontextualized activities. The checklist was used again following the lessons to evaluate how well learner expectations were accommodated while transitioning the students into performing less familiar tasks.

The teacher and students decided to work on neighborhoods because the subject matter was immediately relevant. The students' respective neighborhoods are part of their daily lived experience (where they go shopping, what bus they take to school, where their children go to school, etc.), and neighborhoods are a frequent topic of conversation in daily Pittsburgh life outside the classroom too. Neighborhoods come up frequently because Pittsburghers often talk about their neighborhoods as a way of placing people within the city. And, as Auerbach notes, learning should be contextualized, relevant, and lessons should draw upon the actual experiences and concerns of the learners (Auerbach 1992).

The project began by having the students discuss where in Pittsburgh they lived. The students asked each other "Where do you live?" As students named their neighborhoods, more proficient students wrote the different neighborhoods on the board. Everyone helped with the spelling on the board. After introducing the topic orally and with some words written on the board, the class then used color photos to develop vocabulary related to things the students would see in their neighborhood like school, park, bank, etc. Studies have shown that nonliterate subjects are better at naming two-dimensional representations of real objects when presented as colored photos as compared to black and white drawings (Reis 2006 as cited in Elson & Krygowski 2012). The students then used cards with the vocabulary words to match to the picture cards. After associating the words with the appropriate pictures, the students then used the picture cards and word cards to play games and ask each other what they see in their neighborhood. In short, the students talked a lot, interacted with pictures, single words, and a few short sentences before they began reading and writing about their neighborhoods.

Rather than using text as a starting point, as is often done in Western classrooms, the instructor capitalized on the students oral capabilities and familiarity with the subject matter through images and only then began to introduce text and print. Likewise, even after text was introduced, the teacher, using the checklist as a reminder or prompt, was mindful to use print and oral interaction in tandem to consistently ground the less familiar element of print in the familiarity of the spoken word. The language and content are familiar because the students are using language to recall and retell what they already know about, heard about, or have experienced (Marshall & DeCapua 2013: 64-65).

Following this gradual introduction of print, the class read a story about the teacher's neighborhood, first chorally and in partners (shared responsibility) and then one-by-one (individual accountability). The class asked questions about the story (decontextualized learning/academic) like "Is there a school in her neighborhood?" The students must re-read or scan the story for this information. Though the task of looking for the information may be new, it is scaffolded through what is now familiar vocabulary and subject matter.

The final part of this unit is when the students then completed a cloze activity or used sentence frames based on the original story to share about their own neighborhood and the things they see in it. More proficient students were given more open-ended sentence prompts.

Using the stories the students wrote, the teacher then compiled the LEAs into a booklet to use for further activities in class. Since it is a Bridge Literacy class, many of the activities were intended to build literacy, as well phonics and phonemic awareness. Rather than introduce such unfamiliar tasks with decontextualized phonics lessons, phonics and phonemic awareness were taught in the context of the students' own stories. When students are familiar with a given topic and have a bank of words, teachers can then spend time on sound-symbol correspondence, and learners can discover how letters and sounds are related (Brod 1999: 16, as cited in Vinogradov 2010).

One of these literacy activities included asking students to sort key words from other students' stories based on the sound of the first letter. This required the decontextualized task of sorting as well as phonemic awareness, but did so using familiar, student-generated words. Other academic or decontextualized tasks students did were:

- answered comprehension questions about the stories
- practiced syntax using sentences from students' own stories
- compared and contrast two different students' stories

- students from same neighborhood worked in groups to create a short “Our Neighborhood” summary, focusing on using the first person, plural pronoun and possessive pronoun *we* and *our*.

Figure 3: *Sara’s Bridge Literacy class sort key words from their stories based on first letter sound and write them on posters around the class.*

Through use of the MALP model, the teacher was able to use the students’ comfort with speaking and familiarity with their own neighborhoods as the basis for gaining confidence in participating in new, decontextualized classroom tasks. The students worked on immediately relevant content about where they live and their community, and were given the opportunity to share about themselves and their neighborhood with others and the teacher to develop interconnectedness. The students gained facility with the written word by using it along with the spoken word when doing scaffolding activities, composing and reading their neighborhood LEAs. The students were accountable to their own individual learning as well since they ultimately each composed their own neighborhood story, but did so only after sharing the responsibility by helping each other write and spell at the board, asking each other questions, and participating in vocabulary review together. While working on material that was relevant, contextualized, and engaging, the students were able to get to know each other and the teacher, and the students were then more at ease and willing to participate in new, decontextualized tasks, such as sorting words, practicing phonemic awareness, and syntax. These decontextualized tasks were made

more accessible to our LESLLA students through their own experiences and words they used to talk about something relevant to their own lives.

3.2. Allegra's Foundations class

In Allegra's morning Foundations class, the MALP model was implemented with Bhutanese, Burmese and Iraqi refugee students who scored at a 0-1 SPL/Beginning ESOL literacy, with most of the students scoring under 200 on the Best Plus. While the class size varies it is one of the larger classes at GPLC with 15-20 students regularly. Most have very limited or no experience with formal education. When these students enter the class they range from no ability in English to minimum functioning skills, understanding isolated words to a limited number of simple learned phrases. It can be difficult to communicate with students at this level. This fact can skew the class towards being more teacher-centered and less MALP-like. Given that students with more oral language facility have more success with literacy (see Cloud, Genesee, & Hamayan 2009), this class focusses primarily on oral communication, improving students' ability around listening and speaking before tackling reading and writing. The class is based strongly in routine, following a logical, progressive sequence with a good deal of recycling of concepts. Every day starts with a beginning routine that encompasses small talk and social etiquette. We work with simple language chunks such as *How are you? Where are you from? How's the weather?* As the MALP implementation began, Allegra looked at ways to link oral transmission with the written word and pragmatic tasks with academic tasks.

In order to progress from the basic *How are you? Good, thanks. And you? /Good, thanks.*, the teacher began to think of ways to help students express more of their genuine feelings. This would help with interconnectedness in and outside of the classroom. Based on what she knew about the students' lives she narrowed down a large feelings list to 10 feelings on which to focus: *happy, sad, tired, hungry, thirsty, relaxed, angry, confused, excited, bored*. With the aim of initially introducing the students to these feelings in English, time was spent with color photos of people vividly expressing these feelings. The photos showed people of different ages and ethnicities. Once students mastered the color photos, handouts with the same photos were printed in black and white. Students began expressing these feelings as they related to them, and it became part of the beginning routine, a check-in to get a better read on how the students were doing on a daily basis.

To help expand the Feelings activity Allegra decided to design a project that would show current students' comprehension of the activity, solidify a routine, and welcome new students given that the class, like all classes at GPLC, is open entry / open exit. With posters, markers, and magazines, the students began creating feelings posters to be hung on the classroom walls. The teacher wrote the feeling word on the poster, and students began looking through magazines to find pictures that illustrated these feelings. They worked in groups, cut out pictures and glued them around the word. They then visited each other's groups to see what everyone had created. Finally the posters were hung around the classroom where everyone could see them.

Together these activities constituted a MALP project. Project-based learning views instruction as the development of knowledge and skills in service of a culminating student product that demonstrates mastery (DeCapua & Marshall, 2011: 61). Project-based learning is ideal for integrating MALP into classes for struggling L2 learners. As described by DeCapua & Marshall (2011: 84), it: "encourages immediate relevance, allows for differentiation, supports group work while requiring individual accountability, easily integrates oral transmission and print, provides a framework for introducing, practicing, and recycling language, content, and ways of thinking." In this case the Feelings posters project was immediately relevant because students often indicated that they wanted to express their feelings to their teachers and each other. They were able to share important personal information and have a deeper relationship with each other. Students developed and maintained interconnectedness as they were able to express their feelings more freely and confidently and also understand each other's feeling. For example, one day a student pointed to the 'angry' poster and said "I'm angry." Another student responded to this student, saying "Why?" and the first student replied "Bus late." True communication was happening. The posters helped move the class away from being teacher-centered. It gave the students the ability to have a conversation without teacher prompts. In terms of shared and individual responsibility, students participated by choosing their own photos but then deciding as a group if they fit the emotion.

There was also a blend of oral transmission with print during the lesson and afterwards. While the teacher wrote the Feelings words on the posters, students then talked about them as they looked for pictures; some students wrote the Feeling words in their notebooks and later would review them while looking at the posters. When new students started class, current students would point out the posters and talk about them. Students participated in academic ways of thinking by categorizing, sorting, and choosing the best pictures. They did this with familiar language and content already reviewed in class. The posters

continue to hang on the classroom walls helping with integration of new students and communication of true feelings.

Figure 4: A student-created feelings poster, 'Hungry', hanging in Allegra's foundations class.

3.3. Katie's family literacy class

At the Families for Learning Family Literacy site, Katie implemented the model with two very large (19 families total, with 17 individual children) multi-level classes. Her students (mainly young mothers and their children) are from Burma, Bhutan, Tanzania, Democratic Republic of Congo, Iraq and Mexico. Their scores ranged from 2 to 5 SPL levels on the Best Plus test. The families and teacher worked together to plan, organize, create, and hang a 5 by 9 foot long mural on their site's wall. The mural project was developed as a result of students expressing a desire to decorate the site.

The adult learners discussed and developed the design with little input from their instructor. The mural depicts a large oak tree, the national tree of the United States, with flowers representing the student families' countries of origin. The oak tree has construction paper leaves that families colored together, using designs of their choosing. The mural is bordered by national flags of all the families' cultures of origin, along with the American flag. The flags alternate with handprints of children from the site.

Figure 5: *The student-created mural hanging in the Families for learning site.*

The project's content and subject matter were selected because they had immediate relevancy to the students. The goal of the project was for the mural to decorate the space where families have class. The symbols chosen for the mural were also immediately relevant since they represent the students' countries of birth. The mural was largely a collaborative process with students working together on planning and sketching, painting the tree, helping the children do their handprints, and finally assembling and hanging the mural itself. Such collaboration maintained the strong interconnectedness of working together that many LESLLA families prefer. The collaboration incorporated shared responsibility, but there was individual responsibility also, since individual components like the leaves, flowers, and flags were done by each particular family. The project was also accessible in content. Though the students may never have made a mural before, many of these adult learners have experience in fabric arts. Thus the process of planning and creating something decorative made of different component pieces was not new.

After the mural project was completed, the class reflected on and summarized the process of creating it through a series of literacy activities. Like the actual project, the literacy activities followed the model in their planning and implementation as well. A group LEA text was created in each of the two classes. The students produced group reflections on the mural (shared responsibility) as well as individual ones (individual accountability) in which learners described their personal contributions. These two student-created texts were used as the basis for literacy lessons and reading comprehension tasks done in class. The

literacy-based tasks (written word) were scaffolded through oral interaction as the language and content in these documents had already been orally reviewed before and during the creation of the mural. Using these texts as models, many learners then composed their own individual texts summarizing what they had done with their children to contribute to the mural. When the texts were finished, two copies of each story were printed. One was laminated and given to the writer; the other became part of a book documenting the project. Writing individual summaries gave learners an opportunity to focus on academic, decontextualized tasks like summarizing, writing, and revising.

The finished mural is now hanging up at the site next to the two LEAs reflecting on it; it makes the whole room look more friendly, personalized, and family-centered, creating a more MALP learning environment overall.

4. Successes and challenges

As we shifted our instructional model in these classes, successes and challenges presented themselves readily. While the successes can be difficult to quantify by looking at class data, we are able to address them here qualitatively.

Implementing the model was extremely successful in that it kept the teachers focused on making lesson plans that were immediately relevant, less teacher-centered, and combined shared and individual responsibility as well as oral and written components. In particular, the MALP checklist helped to create more successful lessons as we were accountable for making sure each lesson accepted student conditions for learning, combined LESLLA as well as Western-style learning processes while beginning to introduce students to decontextualized classroom tasks.

We were also able to develop greater continuity from lesson to lesson as well as between different classes. It encouraged us to be more reflective about where we've been and where we're going in terms of projects and lessons, having us constantly referring back to the MALP checklist to guide our thinking. Because multiple teachers worked on the implementation, we were also able to think more about how to transition students from one class into the next.

We found that focusing on using oral transmission to scaffold reading and writing skills helped with building student confidence, and that having students take more responsibility in the classroom and help create their own materials generated a sense of pride and ownership of their class as well.

Students developed even stronger bonds with each other through working together on the projects. Many students learned that they shared a lot in common and asked each other further questions about their lives outside class.

For instance, in Sara's Bridge class two students, one from Iran and one from Bhutan, realized that they shared the same neighborhood, they started planning bus trips to school together and also walking together in their neighborhood, pointing out good places to shop.

The challenges that continue to present themselves are in the form of erratic attendance due to family issues and extreme weather, the necessary but, at times, daunting and distracting open entry/open exit policy, students leaving suddenly for full-time jobs, and some students giving up prematurely because they don't see progress happening fast enough. We are continuing to try and address these challenges by restructuring class levels, implementing MALP across these levels, encouraging interconnectedness, incorporating relevant content, and experimenting with flipped learning in hopes that it will be easier for students to orient and re-orient to the class.

5. Next steps and conclusion

As we move forward, we continue to use the model to plan more ways to utilize it in the classroom. We frequently refer back to the checklist to guide our thinking about how to structure student-lead projects and the activities leading up to them that best transition students into successful participation in the classroom and help them master new content and vocabulary.

We will continue to work together with Drs. Marshall and DeCapua to provide feedback both ways. We'll discuss both what in the model we have successes and difficulty with, and what the model does and doesn't address in our classrooms. The researchers will provide us with more feedback on how better to use the model, as well as help us generate new ideas for structuring and organizing our classes.

In terms of future directions, we plan to train new ESL instructors at GPLC in the model in order to have consistency across classes. By training these instructors in MALP, we hope to help smooth the transition into working with students with more limited educational backgrounds and ease both teacher and student frustration since our new instructors are often unfamiliar with working with LESLLA students.

Innovation and new ways of thinking about instruction are essential elements to working with LESLLA students. It is important for researchers and practitioners to continue to work together in meaningful ways to support students and one another. To this end, we have begun discussing, presenting, and publishing our experiences working together with Drs. DeCapua and Marshall while using the MALP model in our classrooms. This article marks the

first effort towards that end, but we hope to continue such work by making publishable, ready-to-use classroom materials to share with other instructors and volunteers looking for more effective ways of engaging with LESLLA students.

Acknowledgements

The presentation at the LESLLA conference was adapted from a presentation at COABE (Commission on Adult Basic Education) in 2014 with Andrea DeCapua, Helaine Marshall, and Katie Murphy. We are grateful for their continued support and work.

Thank you to Katie Murphy for allowing us to adapt her writings for this project.

Notes

- 1 MALP® and Mutually Adaptive Learning Paradigm® are registered trademarks of MALP, LLC. For terms and conditions of use, contact information@malpeducation.com.
- 2 The BEST Plus assessment was created by the Center for Applied Linguistics, and more information can be found at: <http://www.cal.org/aea/bestplus/index.html>.

References

- Auerbach, E. (1992). *Making meaning, making change: Participatory curriculum development for adult ESL literacy*. Center for Applied Linguistics and Delta Systems, Washington, DC and McHenry, IL.
- Brod, S. (1999). *What non-readers or beginning readers need to know: Performance-based ESL Literacy*. Denver, CO: Spring Institute for International Studies.
- Cloud, N., Genesee, F., & Hamayan, E. (2009). *Literacy instruction for English language learners*. Portsmouth, NH: Heinemann.
- Condelli, L., & Wrigley, H. S. (2006). Instruction, language and literacy: What works study for adult ESL literacy students. In I. van de Craats, J. Kurvers, & M. Young-Scholten (eds.), *Low-Educated adult Second Language and Literacy Acquisition: Proceedings of the inaugural symposium* (pp. 111–133). Utrecht, The Netherlands: LOT.
- DeCapua, A., & Marshall, H.W. (2010). Serving ELLs with limited or interrupted education: Intervention that works. *TESOL Journal*, 1, 49-70.

- DeCapua, A., & Marshall, H.W. (2011). *Breaking new ground: Teaching English learners with limited or interrupted formal Education in US secondary schools*. Ann Arbor, MI: University of Michigan Press.
- DeCapua, A., & Marshall, H.W. (2011). Reaching ELLs at Risk: Instruction for Students with Limited/Interrupted Formal Education. *Preventing School Failure, 55*, 35-41.
- DeCapua, A., & Marshall, H.W. (2015). *Promoting achievement for English learners with limited or interrupted formal education: A culturally responsive approach*. Principal Leadership, National Association of Secondary School Principals, 48-51.
- Elson, A., & Krygowski, N. (2012). Low-Level Learners: Prioritizing Teaching Topics. In P. Vinogradov & M. Bigelow (eds.), *Low-Educated Second Language and Literacy Acquisition: Proceedings of the 7th Symposium*, Minneapolis, 2012, 183-202.
- Ibarra, R. (2001). *Beyond affirmative action: Reframing the context of higher education*. Madison: The University of Wisconsin Press.
- Marshall, H.W., & DeCapua, A. (2013). *Making the transition to classroom success: Culturally responsive teaching for struggling language learners*. Ann Arbor: University of Michigan Press.
- Marshall, H. W. (1994). Hmong/English bilingual adult literacy project. Final report of research conducted under the National Institute for Literacy, grant #X257A20457. University of Wisconsin-Green Bay.
- Marshall, H. W. (1998). A mutually adaptive learning paradigm (MALP) for Hmong students. *Cultural Circles, 3*, 134-141.
- Nieto, S., (2010). *Language, culture, and teaching: Critical Perspectives* (2nd ed.) NewYork: Routledge.
- Reis, A. (2006). Color makes a difference: Two-dimensional object naming in literate and illiterate subjects. *Brain and Cognition, 60*(1), 49-54.
- Van Allen, R. & Allen, C. (1967). *Language experience activities*. Boston: Houghton-Mifflin.
- Vinogradov, P. (2010). Balancing top and bottom: Learner-generated texts for teaching phonics. In T. Wall & M. Leong (eds.), *Low-Educated Second Language and Literacy Acquisition: Proceedings of the 5th symposium*, Calgary, 2010, 3-14.

Appendix

MALP[®] Teacher Planning Checklist

A. Accept Conditions for Learning
A1. I am making this lesson/project immediately relevant to my students.
A2. I am helping students develop and maintain interconnectedness.
B. Combine Processes for Learning
B1. I am incorporating both shared responsibility and individual accountability.
B2. I am scaffolding the written word through oral interaction.
C. Focus on New Activities for Learning
C1. I am focusing on tasks requiring academic ways of thinking.
C2. I am making these tasks accessible to my students with familiar language and content.

© University of Michigan Press, 2011. DeCapua, A. & Marshall, H.W.
Breaking New Ground: Teaching Students with Limited or Interrupted Formal Education in U.S. Secondary Schools.